

Assessing Community Livelihood Assets and Tourism Development Readiness through the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework: The Case of Kutubdia Island, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is frequently promoted as a livelihood diversification strategy for coastal and island communities. However, many coastal and island destinations remain underdeveloped due to uneven local capacities. This study addresses a critical gap in the literature by examining community readiness for tourism development prior to tourism intervention using an asset-based analytical lens. Focusing on Kutubdia Island in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh, the study applies the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) to assess the status of five livelihood capitals - human, social, natural, financial, and physical capital- and how these capitals shape community preparedness and willingness to engage in tourism. The paper adopts a qualitative exploratory research design based on 25 semi-structured interviews with local community members representing diverse livelihood groups, including fishers, farmers, small business owners, teachers, and service-sector workers in Kutubdia Island. The findings indicate relatively strong social capital reflected in community cohesion, trust, and hospitality. Human capital is at a moderate level, with educational aspirations present but limited tourism-specific skills. Natural capital is abundant and diverse, but it remains highly vulnerable to environmental degradation. Financial capital is unevenly distributed and poorly organized. Limited physical capital, especially in transportation, accommodation, healthcare, and basic tourism infrastructure, is the main problem. The study shows that having a high level of community readiness and acceptance is not enough for tourism development if there is no basic physical capital. It provides evidence that using the SLF approach to assessing tourism readiness in early development stages is highly valuable. This offers useful insights for policymakers and tourism planners working on connecting tourism projects with local abilities in vulnerable island areas.

1. Introduction

Tourism is widely recognized for its contribution to livelihood diversification and local economic development in many developing countries. It is also recognized as one of the world's biggest economic sectors that supports jobs and generates export

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revenues for almost all countries across the globe. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council's (WTTC) Economic Impact Report, the tourism sector contributed approximately 10% to the global economy in 2024, generating USD 10.9 trillion, an 8.5% increase from 2023 and about 6% above pre-pandemic levels (WTTC 2025). In 2025, the sector reached a record contribution of USD 11.6 trillion, accounting for 9.8% of global GDP (WTTC 2026). Also, the sector supported a total of 366 million jobs globally in 2025, which is approximately 1 in 9 jobs. Tourism, with proper design and management, can effectively provide jobs and small business opportunities to local communities, and thus increase community resilience. However, in many remote and resource-dependent areas, tourism development is still limited by poor infrastructure, unequal distribution of benefits, and environmental problems. These challenges show the importance of assessing community readiness and livelihood capacity before promoting tourism as a development strategy.

Bangladesh has a long coastline and many offshore islands, which create strong tourism potential. Many smaller islands are often ignored in national tourism planning while destinations like Cox's Bazar and Saint Martin's Island have been centred in policy making. An example of such islands is Kutubdia Island in the Cox's Bazar District of Bangladesh (Rahman et al. 2014). Despite having wide sea beaches, salt fields, fisheries, cultural and spiritual heritage sites, and renewable energy infrastructure, Kutubdia has not developed as a recognised tourism destination. However, the physical infrastructure, environmental degradation, and institutional support remain critical issues on the island hampering the growth of tourism and livelihood diversification.

In the context of Kutubdia, assessing tourism potential involves more than only identifying natural attractions or market demand. The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) provides a useful framework for understanding community livelihoods and sustainability in both developing and developed countries (Tao and Wall 2009) and assessing livelihood sustainability across both developing and developed contexts (Snider, 2012). The strength of the SLF lies in its recognition of the complexity of people's lives and its focus on community interests in the development process through the analysis of human, social, financial, natural, and physical capital assets. The SLF is especially relevant for the systematic analysis of existing livelihood resources and the preparedness of the local community to participate in future tourism development for Kutubdia Island, where tourism development is still not significantly developed. Many international organizations and governments support sustainable development and sustainable tourism. However, these concepts are often lacking visual clarity and difficult to apply at the local level.

In many destinations, sustainability remains a predetermined named goal rather than an operational guide for development. In small island contexts, where unplanned tourism can quickly lead to visible social and environmental pressures, there is a need for approaches that maintain the overall sustainability that is going to aid the local community in the long run. Accordingly, this study adopts the SLF to assess community

livelihood assets, providing an asset-based and context-sensitive basis for examining the potential for tourism development in Kutubdia Island.

Based on this analytical framing, the study aims to address the following objectives:

1. To assess the current status of community livelihood assets (human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital) in Kutubdia Island in relation to tourism development.
2. To analyse how existing livelihood assets shape community preparedness and willingness to engage in future tourism development in Kutubdia Island.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Sustainable Livelihoods Framework

The SLF framework is a paradigm that is popular in understanding both poverty and development (Figure 1). A livelihood, which was first introduced by Chambers and Conway (1991), is a set of people, their abilities and the ways of living, income and assets, and it is said to be sustainable when it sustains or improves the asset base on which it relies. Based on this concept, the framework designed by the Department for International Development (DFID) focuses on five types of capital or assets, which are often represented as a pentagon and form the building blocks of the livelihoods (Kollmair and St. Gamper, 2002). These are generally categorised as human capital (skills, knowledge, education, health and other personal capabilities), social capital (social networks, norms, trust and institutional relationships), natural capital (natural resource endowments, land, water, biodiversity, climate), physical capital (infrastructure, technology, equipment and basic services) and financial capital (savings, credit, income and other monetary resources).

Source: DFID 1999.

Collectively, these forms of capital shape the range of options available to individuals and communities in pursuing their livelihoods (Kollmair and St. Gamper, 2002; Yenikalaycı and Kayasu, 2025). These assets are placed in a more expansive vulnerability framework of exposure to shocks, trends, and seasonality, and within the structure/processes (institutions, policies, and markets) that mediate the nature of assets to livelihood strategies and outcomes by the SLF. In this regard, the SLF offers a multidimensional analytical lens: instead of concentrating on the concept of income, it examines how all five forms of capital affect the ability of people to attain sustainable livelihoods within specific socio-economic and environmental contexts (Kollmair and St. Gamper, 2002).

2.2. SLF in Tourism and Rural Development

The SLF has been widely used in analysing the nexus between tourism and rural development. Tourism is often promoted as a mechanism for poverty alleviation and socio-economic development in rural areas and the SLF is used by researchers to assess whether tourism can deliver practical effects to community livelihood. Alam (2025) explicitly utilizes the SLF to investigate sustainable tourism in rural Bangladesh, in which the framework's central elements - vulnerable context, livelihood resources, institutional organization, and process - can be applied to the development of tourism-generated livelihood opportunities. Similarly, Pasanchay and Schott (2021) used SLF to measure the community homestays of rural areas in Laos and consider tourism as one of the various livelihood sources, and assessed its broader impacts on community well-being.

These empirical applications consistently indicate that tourism development involves all five types of assets indicated by the SLF. For instance, infrastructure improvements (physical capital) and tourist spending (financial capital) can arise from tourism, while training and health services (human capital) may expand as a result of tourism-linked projects (Alam 2025). However, studies note that benefits are highly mediated by local assets and governance. A critical review emphasizes that simply introducing tourism does not automatically secure sustainable livelihoods; rather, pre-existing capital endowments, social networks and institutional context must be aligned with tourism strategies (Shen, Hughey, and Simmons 2008). In other words, tourism's overall effect on community development depends on how well it integrates with the community's asset base and on the strengths of local organisations and backup policies.

In many developing regions, households are involved in different economic activities such as farming, fishing, guiding, hospitality, and handicrafts to increase their income (Abdurakhmanova and Ahrorov 2025). Studies show that tourism can provide employment (hotels, restaurants, transport) and enable a host of micro-enterprises (homestays, food stalls, craft sales), which can generate cash for the local economy (Pramono and Juliana 2025). For example, coastal villages can use beaches and cultural attractions to create jobs, and communities often use tourism as a way to reduce

poverty and improve their lives. SLF analyses frequently show that tourism can boost household incomes and physical infrastructure that improve livelihoods along with subsistence activities (Alam 2025; Liu, Dupre, Wang, and Jin 2025).

Nevertheless, tourism also brings significant risks and trade-offs. Previous findings show that the benefits of tourism are not always shared equally. In one small-island Indonesian case, researchers observed that many tourism profits were captured by a few local elites or investors, while most local people received limited benefits; moreover, low levels of education and skills constrained local participation in tourism employment (Pramono and Juliana 2025). In some areas, tourism is highly seasonal with fewer tourists. Thus, the community's income also reduces significantly during off-seasons. As a result, many people return to their traditional occupation during those times (Su et al. 2022). This seasonality can create income gaps and uncertainty. Heavy dependency on tourism. It also makes local communities vulnerable to external pressure such as political instability, inflation, or pandemics. During the COVID-19 pandemic, this vulnerability became clear when tourism-dependent communities suddenly lost their main sources of income (Sun et al. 2022). However, tourism often creates both opportunities and difficulty of job creation.

2.3. The Role of Livelihood Assets in Tourism Participation

Livelihood assets play an important role in community participation in tourism. Human capital such as education, training, language skills, and health, affects people's ability to be involved in tourism-related jobs or start tourism-related businesses. At the community level, people with limited skills often work in low-paid or informal jobs, while training and capacity building can help local people gain more benefits from tourism (Shen, Hughey, and Simmons, 2008; Ari et al., 2025). Social capital refers to trust, social networks, and local institutions, which influence tourism management and benefit sharing. Strong social relationships can support community-based tourism (CBT), while weak social cohesion may lead to conflict, unequal benefits, and elite control (Arizkha et al., 2023; Moscardo et al., 2017). Coastal and island tourism depends on natural capital that includes the beauty of coastal ecosystems and scenic shorelines, which draw tourists' attention and the enjoyment of activities like beach recreation, snorkelling, and wildlife viewing. Environmental degradation, biodiversity loss, and habitat destruction can reduce the attractiveness of tourism destinations and threaten livelihood stability (Arabadzhyan et al., 2022; Uribe et al., 2023). Physical and financial capital also affect tourism participation. Infrastructure such as roads, ports, and utilities support tourism development, while poor connectivity can limit local participation, especially in remote areas (Khadaroo and Seetana, 2008; Hesna et al., 2025). Financial capital, including credit and investment, helps community members to start tourism-related businesses, whereas limited financial access can hamper livelihood diversification (Kitole and Sesabo, 2024).

In general, SLF assets influence tourism readiness in different but connected ways. As human and social capital shape community skills and organization, natural capital

provides the resource base, and physical and financial capital support participation in tourism activities. Therefore, the SLF highlights the importance of balanced asset development, as tourism without proper skills, infrastructure, and environmental protection can lead to dependency and resource degradation (Pramono and Juliana, 2025; Yenikalaycı and Kayasu, 2025).

2.4. Challenges of Small Islands and Gaps in the Literature

Small islands and coastal villages face several structural challenges such as limited land, remote locations, and narrow economic opportunities. These factors affect both tourism potential and livelihood vulnerability. Geographical isolation increases transportation costs, reduces market access and limits economic growth including tourism development (Scandurra et al., 2018). These challenges are further increased by climate-related risks as islands are highly vulnerable to sea-level rise, storms, erosion, and flooding. And these can damage ecosystems, tourism infrastructure, and traditional livelihoods like fishing and agriculture (Pathak et al., 2021; Wolf et al., 2021).

Research on coastal and inland areas shows that natural and physical assets are highly vulnerable to climate and disaster risks. Such as poor infrastructure, dependency on boat transportation, irregular transport services and limited livelihood options often can discourage tourism investment. Similar conditions can be seen in the islands of Bangladesh, where weak connectivity and limited basic services reduce economic opportunities (Islam, 2024). Economic dependency on fishing, farming and remittances also increases vulnerability to external shocks. Although tourism may create opportunities for income diversification, yet it also can increase vulnerability if it is not supported by stronger community assets and infrastructure. From the SLF perspective, this highlights the importance of balancing tourism development with risk reduction and asset improvement. Although research on tourism and livelihoods is growing, however, several important research gaps still remain. Much of the existing research addresses tourism and sustainable livelihoods separately or focuses on a single dimension of the issue. According to the study by Liu et al. (2025), the knowledge on the SLF in tourism studies is still viewed in a fragmented fashion with few studies attempting to make a full integration of livelihood and tourism frameworks. Similarly, Shen et al. (2008) pointed out that direct application of the classic SLF to tourism is inadequate as the sector features require a contextualised version of the SLF to Tourism, one that considers sector-specific dynamics.

Empirically, there is a large number of studies evaluating the impacts of tourism when post-development has taken place (e.g., measuring changes in incomes or perceptions by the community), but relatively few studies evaluate community preparedness or capacity for tourism in an ex-ante asset-based way (Sarnacchiaro & Ariante, 2025). In other words, there remains a lack of research that systematically maps local livelihood assets against tourism opportunities before the initiation of large-scale tourism projects. Overall, the existing literature indicates the necessity of more integrated,

asset-based measures of tourism preparedness. This gap could be addressed in studies integrating the five-capital SLF with tourism planning, especially when it comes to small island situations like Kutubdia. By addressing these gaps, tourism development can be better aligned with local strengths and constraints, rather than being imposed through uniform, one-size-fits-all development models.

3. Context: Kutubdia Island, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh

The study area, Kutubdia Island, is located in the south-eastern coast of Bangladesh (21°42'18"N to 21°57'45"N latitude and 91°47'25"E to 91°25'27"E longitude). Administratively, it is an Upazila (sub-district) of Cox's Bazar District (Figure 2). It is separated from the mainland by the Kutubdia Channel and is highly vulnerable to the sea level rise, storm and coastal erosion (Rahman and Schmidlin 2019; Rahman et al. 2017). The island has an area of around 112 km² and an average elevation of less than 3m above sea level (Rahman and Schmidlin, 2019). Its population is predominantly Bengali Muslim and mostly dependent on agriculture, salt production and fishing for their livelihood. This island is also famous for the production of dry fish.

Figure 2. Location of Kutubdia, Bangladesh. Source: Rahman et al. 2014.

Kutubdia Island consists of six unions and twenty-nine villages. As per the Bangladesh Population Census in 2022, the population of the island was 1,43,619 (BBS 2022). Like other coastal zones of Bangladesh, the livelihoods of Kutubdia Island mainly depend on agriculture and fishing. Fishing communities are often located close to the shoreline and are therefore vulnerable to environmental hazards. Coastal erosion forces fisher families to often abandon their ancestral homes and face additional threats to their lives and livelihoods from frequent cyclones and storms. Most people in Kutubdia are poor and live in simple small bamboo and straw houses that are weak and easily damaged. The coastal region is generally poorer in income than many other parts of Bangladesh.

4. Methodology

This study used an exploratory research design using qualitative semi-structured interviews grounded in the SLF to assess community livelihood assets and their readiness for participate in tourism businesses in Kutubdia Island, Bangladesh. An exploratory design was considered suitable due to the limited empirical studies on tourism-related livelihood readiness in small offshore islands and there is no structured tourism development on Kutubdia so far. The study focused on current livelihood conditions and community perceptions instead of measuring impacts after tourism development. Qualitative semi-structured interviews are widely used commonly in tourism and livelihood research involving resident communities, particularly when the aim is to understand local community perceptions, organisational structures, policy initiatives, and their impacts (Tao et al. 2010; Snider, 2012; Su et al. 2019). Therefore, face-to-face in-depth interviews were selected as the primary data collection method and conducted with community members.

In total, 25 semi-structured qualitative interviews with community members were conducted. Data were collected during fieldwork conducted in November 2024. Data saturation occurred after conducting around 20 interviews, though a total of 25 interviews were conducted for ensuring precision of the data (Islam, Kabir, and Hassan 2022; Saunders et al. 2018). Participants were selected purposively (Patton 2002) to identify with relevant knowledge of local livelihoods and community dynamics. Participants included fishermen, salt farmers, business owners, teachers, drivers, students, and service workers to ensure diverse perspectives across different livelihood groups. **Table 1** provides a list of participants with a summary of interviews conducted.

Table 1. Details of the local community participants.

No	Participants' names/ Pseudonyms	Profession	Age	Gender	Level of education	Length of Interview (minutes)
1	Sadek	Teacher	55	Male	Post Graduate	37
2	Gias	Local Residents	30	Male	High School	25
3	Eskender	Local Shopkeeper	28	Male	High School	40
4	Meskat	Waiter	21	Male	High School	22
5	Khokon	Tailor	26	Male	Primary Level	34
6	Sabit	Local Student	20	Male	Undergraduate	36
7	Khalek	Fisherman	55	Male	No Education	28
8	Tanvir	Local Student	20	Male	High School	48
9	Yasin	Local Businessman	18	Male	High School	24
10	Kaisar	Fisherman	35	Male	High School	52
11	Shetu	Journalist	31	Male	Primary Level	61
12	Akash	Student	22	Male	Undergraduate	52
13	Shahadat	Local Businessman	28	Male	High School	26
14	Sabrina	Teacher	24	Female	Graduate	34
15	Faruk	Advocate	45	Male	Post Graduate	42
16	Hafiz	Auto-rickshaw Driver	20	Male	Primary level	24
17	Islam	Driver	23	Male	High School	22
18	Amirul	Hotel Owner	27	Male	Post Graduate	75
19	Mominul	Tea Stall Owner	52	Male	No Education	43
20	Amir	Salt Farmer	28	Male	Primary level	42
21	Omor	School Principal	45	Male	Post Graduate	41
22	Sumir	Teacher	55	Male	Post Graduate	26
23	Islam	Auto-rickshaw Driver	37	Male	No Education	36
24	Jayed	Imam of a Masjid	42	Male	Graduate	54
25	Shila	Office Assistant	60	Female	High School	60

The average length of the interview was approximately 40 minutes. Participants' names and occupational identities were disclosed with their prior consent, as they agreed to be identified for contextual clarity and transparency of their perspectives. Interviews were conducted face-to-face in the local language (Bangla), then all interviews were digitally recorded, transcribed verbatim, and subsequently translated into English for analysis. The data were analysed using a manual thematic approach, in which the transcripts were systematically coded and examined through content analysis and thematic coding techniques (Creswell et al. 2007; Islam, Kabir, and Hassan 2022).

The coding process was both theory-driven and data-driven (Islam, Ruhanen, and Ritchie 2018). Broad codes were created based on both the interview data and the literature review. The analysis followed an iterative coding process (Locke, Feldman, and Golden-Biddle 2020). Initial open coding was done to identify recurring ideas that developed from the interview data and these codes were then grouped into broader thematic categories based on the five livelihood assets or capitals of the SLF

(human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital). Themes were further developed through repeated comparison across interviews to identify patterns, deviations, and contextual differences in community livelihood conditions.

All respondents were informed about the purpose of the study before starting the interviews. Participations were voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. The respondents agreed to use their names and their comments in the research article. We took care to represent their views accurately, and not to raise unrealistic expectations about tourism development or external support.

However, this study has some methodological limitations. Firstly, most of the respondents were male, which is reflective of the gendered nature of the livelihoods associated with the coasts and tourism at Kutubdia Island, thus limiting the representation of women's perspectives and the scope for gender-based analysis. Second, purposive sampling was used and participants were selected based on their knowledge of SLF assets. This may have resulted in selection bias, such as the inclusion of more active or socially connected people, and the exclusion of marginalized voices. Third, the qualitative design allowed for a detailed understanding of local perceptions but limits statistical generalisability and thus the findings are only relevant for Kutubdia Island and similar small island contexts.

5. Findings

5.1. Community Livelihood Assets

This paper intends to assess the current situation of community livelihood assets of Kutubdia Island based on the SLF theory. The following section describes five livelihood assets or capitals of local communities living in Kutubdia Island.

5.1.1. Human Capital

Kutubdia Island's human capital shows a mixed profile, while having educated people and motivated youth, but limited skills specific to tourism and limited health care services, indicating inadequate readiness for tourism activities. Local hotel owner Amirul said:

You'll find a lot of educated people in Kutubdia, but they often don't want to stay here due to the local atmosphere; many basic needs and jobs are not available here, that's why people choose to go to Cox's Bazar, Chittagong, or other places to make their livings.

Educated people tend to move from Kutubdia due to limited local opportunities. Supporting this concern, Sadek, a local school teacher, stated, "Here is a shortage of educated and skilled young people. Also, the labour force is small in size it is not easy to find people locally for all kinds of work," suggesting that skill availability does not

align with local development needs. Despite these challenges, respondents highlighted a strong occupational willingness, particularly among young people. A local businessman, Yasin, noted that *“locals, especially the younger generation, are willing to work if given the opportunity, and are ready to learn new skills”*. Similarly, Amir, a salt farmer, explained:

Our local economy is mostly based on fishing and salt production, but our children are continuing their education and hope for higher studies. If tourists come, the educated young will step forward to offer various services. They are well capable and willing to contribute to this sector.

But healthcare facilities were seen as a real limitation. Sabrina, a local school teacher, pointed out that basic treatment is available in the area, stating,

For primary treatments, we have what’s necessary. Since it’s an upazila, there’s a government hospital with doctors, and there is a clinic in the market with pharmacists. For more serious health issues, people usually go to Cox’s Bazar, Chittagong, or Chakaria for treatment. But for minor problems, basic care can be found here.

This limitation was further emphasised by a fisherman named Kaisar, who stated:

If a patient here has a serious condition, the local hospital immediately refers them elsewhere. We don’t have advanced medical care here. To access better treatment, we have to go out of the area. No government-provided transport has ever been available to send patients elsewhere. People have to rent private vehicles and bear all the costs themselves.

The findings show that Kutubdia has real educational potential and a willing workforce. However, the outmigration of skilled people and a lack of proper healthcare infrastructure really hold back the effective use of human capital for tourism development.

5.1.2. Social Capital

The presence of social capital in Kutubdia is the highest; it is all about strong ties, trust, and cooperation among the residents, which is pretty much essential for community-based tourism (CBT). Akash, a local student, described the social environment,

The relationship among locals is very good, although it depends on individual mindsets; there is hardly any conflict here. Kutubdia is very safe. The people are friendly and welcoming. For example, we invited you to sit and chat with us. Most people in Kutubdia are like that.

His point of view shows the overall friendliness and openness of the community, highlighting that most residents maintain positive relationships and perceive the island as safe for both locals and visitors. The cooperative and supportive nature of Kutubdia's social networks was further emphasized by Amir, a salt farmer, who explained:

People here are peaceful. There's no fighting or conflict. We have a peaceful and cooperative environment. Everyone helps each other in times of need, and there's a strong sense of connection among us. We're quite content with this community spirit.

This demonstrates not only low conflict but also the active mutual support and sense of shared responsibility and mutual cooperation, which are essential for community-led tourism initiatives. Faruk, a school principal, highlighted the density of relational networks within the island:

The relationships here are very affectionate. Since the area is small, people form close connections. If you think deeply about it, you'll realise that people here are related to each other in one way or another. Everyone is somehow connected.

This shows the embedded nature of social ties among families and individuals in terms of relations such as family, friendship, and neighbourliness. The presence of social capital in Kutubdia is very high; people have a very cordial bonding among them, as it is a very small area where everyone knows everyone, and they are like a part of a big family. High social capital is an essential element of tourism-readiness because it encourages local participation and helps them in problem-solving, and create hospitable environment for tourists.

5.1.3. Financial Capital

Financial capital in Kutubdia shows significant income potential, mainly from fishing, salt farming, and small local community-owned businesses. However, this potential is weakened by limited savings, weak investment capacity, and a lack of financial planning by the locals, which holds back their long-term economic growth and tourism development. Khalek, a fisherman, pointed out the income-generating potential of local livelihoods, *"There are many big fish, and it's beautiful to see. When we go out to sea, it feels great. Some fishermen even catch fish worth 10 to 12 lakh taka."* He suggests that while lucrative opportunities exist, they are largely linked to natural resources rather than structured financial systems, making their income unstable to mismanagement or external pressures. Despite the potential, income is often spent rapidly rather than savings which limits the capital for future investment. Akash, a local student, described these:

Many people here are linked with the fishing business, but their living standards aren't very developed. For example, when they catch fish, they

eat well, but if they don't, they often struggle. They have a tendency to spend all their earnings quickly. For instance, if they earn 2,000 takas today, they'll spend it all in three days. They don't save for the future. They don't have a saving mindset. which is why their lifestyle doesn't improve much. If they earn 100,000 takas, they'll spend it all within a month. They spend rapidly on tea, cigarettes, and snacks when they come to the market. Instead of eating home-cooked meals, they'll dine at hotels, but they won't invest in good clothes. Their priorities are different from those of salaried workers, who save and spend on things like a nice shirt or a good meal at a restaurant.

This finding suggests that higher income does not necessarily lead to savings, asset accumulation, or long-term investment. As a result, many residents have limited capacity to invest in tourism-related businesses. Limited Infrastructure and limited financial knowledge further limit the effective use of available financial resources. Faruk, a local advocate, explained:

The main sources of income for Kutubdia are fishery and salt production. Here, most people are in the fishing industry. Approximately 90% [of local community members] are illiterate and not familiar with modern technology. They have no concept of things like live fish restaurants, or how tourists might enjoy such experiences. Some people earn good money by fishing, but they don't know how to use the money. With the appropriate infrastructure and guidance, it [Kutubdia] could be a popular tourist destination.

This suggests that without proper education, training, and guidance, even profitable activities cannot be effectively used to support tourism development. As a result, much of the available financial potential remains unused. However, there are still some opportunities for future development. Some locals still have control over their income. a Local student Sabit said:

I don't have to pay any taxes. I don't have to pay taxes to any syndicates. This is my area, so I don't have to pay anyone rent. I can do business on my own land, and all the income will be mine. I won't have to pay rent to anyone.

This suggests that some residents who own land and manage their own businesses are in a better position to benefit from their income. This creates opportunities for local tourism businesses if appropriate guidance, training, and infrastructure support are provided. The financial capital of Kutubdia is strong but uncoordinated and restricted due to the lack of proper guidance. A number of local income sources exist but rapid consumption, lack of financial literacy, external pressures from syndicates and poor infrastructure restrict capital formation and future investment. Without targeted financial support, tourism development may benefit external investors more than local residents.

5.1.4. Natural Capital

Kutubdia's natural capital is very strong, and it acts as a foundation of the island's tourism potential, but it is also highly fragile and vulnerable to degradation. The island is famous for its very wide sea beaches, often said by local people to be wider than the beaches of Cox's Bazar, as well as for casuarina forests, mangroves, and expansive salt fields. Islands like Mayadweep, the historic lighthouse, and the wind power plant are rising islands adding a unique scenic, historical, and infrastructural value. The amount of fresh and dried fish also contributes to local livelihoods and has significant potential for leisure tourism, religious tourism, cultural tourism, and food tourism. A local hotel owner, Amirul, highlighted the island's diverse attractions:

The first and foremost thing is that Kutubdia has the first lighthouse of Bangladesh. Secondly, we are very famous for our dried fish and salt fields. Additionally, we have the shrine of Kutub Awliya and the mausoleum of Malek Shah Huzur, both renowned across Bangladesh. We also have wind energy here.

This shows that the natural resources of Kutubdia are closely linked with its cultural heritage and renewable energy potential, increasing its tourism appeal beyond traditional beach-based attractions. The unique local production of natural products, such as dried fish and salt, further strengthens this potential. Hafiz, an auto-rickshaw driver, described the distinctiveness of Kutubdia's dried fish:

Kutubdia's salt-free dried fish (Shutki) is very famous. Fishermen bring fresh fish from the sea and dry them directly without salt, as the fish are so fresh, they don't spoil. You can see it for yourself and even taste it to confirm there's no salt.

There are vast opportunities for experiential and culinary tourism that are based on local environmental conditions and traditional livelihoods, providing visitors with authentic and unique experiences. The scenic and historical landscape was further expressed by Khokon, a local tailor, who explained:

There are other islands, but Kutubdia is unique. If tourists come here, the first thing they will experience is the presence of a spiritual figure, Shah Abdul Malek (Rah:). His shrine is located here; you will see vast fields of rice on one side, and rows of salt farms on the other. Tourists coming from northern Bangladesh may not know how salt is produced, but here it is done 100% naturally; even some people call us salt engineers. This will be a unique experience for them. The sight of green rice fields and salt piles in the same area is very beautiful.

Despite this richness, a respondent strongly highlights severe environmental threats that threaten environmental sustainability. Jayed, a local imam, pointed out:

There are many trees here, especially casuarina trees, but most of them have been cut down. These trees are the main element that helps

keep Kutubdia safe from soil erosion. The Forest Department often comes and cuts the trees, and some people also extract sand from the embankment area. When sand is removed or used to fill embankments, the trees fall. The Forest Department even sells the trees after cutting them.

These observations clearly point to weaknesses in environmental management institutions, as protective ecosystems are being continuously damaged, making them more vulnerable to erosion and the impacts of climate change. Similarly, Shila, a local resident, highlighted the impacts of weak coastal protection and poor accessibility, stating:

Kutubdia is beautiful in its own way, but beauty alone is not enough without embankments, especially when the sea causes damage across the island and creates serious hardship for local people. Trees are destroyed, and soil erosion brings major problems for residents. Another key issue is crossing the Kutubdia Channel. Tourists often do not visit because of the difficulty of crossing. Even when they are interested, many hesitate due to this.

Her account shows how environmental degradation and accessibility barriers reduce opportunities and hamper tourism development, even though the island has rich natural resources. The natural capital of Kutubdia Island can therefore be seen as both an advantage and a disadvantage. While the island has huge natural, cultural, and scenic resources, these are also exposed to risks due to environmental degradation, weak embankments, and poor policy governance.

5.1.5. Physical Capital

Physical capital in Kutubdia is severely underdeveloped and represents the primary threshold to tourism development, consistently pointed by respondents as the most critical constraint. Despite having strong natural attractions and community acceptance of tourism, poor infrastructure limits visitor access, safety, and comfort, thereby limiting tourism to informal and short-term visits. Amirul, a local hotel owner, highlighted the shortage of accommodation and basic utilities in Kutubdia, stating,

One of the main weaknesses here is the lack of sufficient hotels; there are only two on the entire island. Then there's the issue of drinking water. What's the first thing a person wants after arriving? Water. But here, there is a crisis of safe drinking water. There's no proper system for fresh water; most of it is salty. The government should install deep tube wells to provide safe drinking water. Many people don't have the ability to buy bottled water.

This indicates that the lack of essential services, such as accommodation and safe drinking water, immediately reduces visitor satisfaction and discourages longer stays.

Transport and road infrastructure were also repeatedly identified as major limitations. Islam, a driver, explained, "Our roads are very narrow. The main road here is only 9 to 12 feet wide. If they were wider, it would be better. Two large vehicles can't cross each other. Even two jeeps can't pass side by side." He further added:

It would be great if the beach were kept clean, if there were seats on the beach for people to sit, and if there were large hotels. People would come here to stay 5-6 days, but since there are no proper accommodations, they leave. Just now, I dropped off a tourist at Baraghop Ghat. They also said there's no good hotel to stay in. I told them, "One day, things will improve, and you should visit again." I told them we have open beaches here. They asked, "Is this a hotel?" That's why having a good hotel in Kutubdia would be great.

These observations show that poor road conditions, limited public facilities, and insufficient accommodation directly reduce the length of tourist stays and discourage repeat visits. As Kutubdia is a remote island, challenges related to accessibility and coastal protection further increase these challenges. Meskat, a local restaurant waiter, pointed to the lack of safe and reliable transport and embankments, stating,

Many people have suggested building a bridge. However, I don't think building a bridge is possible here. But if there were a ferry service, it would definitely make things easier. People wouldn't be afraid anymore. Right now, people are scared of the small boats and Danish boats. These boats are unstable, and people are afraid to travel on them. The main issue is the lack of a permanent embankment. There's no permanent embankment here. They keep saying it will be built, but it hasn't happened. The sandbag system is in place, but it gets washed away every year when the water level rises.

This highlights how unreliable transport and weak coastal infrastructure not only limit tourism development but also increase environmental vulnerability. Healthcare sector is also critically insufficient, particularly in emergency situations, further reduce the island's capacity to support safe and sustainable tourism. Sabit, a local student, stated, "The biggest issue is emergency delivery system for women. Our Kutubdia hospital doesn't have the necessary equipment for delivering babies." This reflects broader concerns about safety and risk, which negatively influence both tourism readiness and resident well-being.

Finally, Kaiser, a local fisherman, emphasised how isolation and neglect amplify physical constraints, explaining:

Kutubdia is an island surrounded by the sea, and people visit it because it is an island. However, the sea itself acts as a barrier. During the rainy season, the sea becomes rough and people are unable to travel. If a ferry service were available, visitors could come at any time. At present, the island feels completely neglected. There is also no

permanent embankment around Kutubdia, which is a major issue. If embankments were in place, more people in the country would likely invest effort in developing this area.

All these findings show how physical isolation, seasonal inaccessibility, and the lack of proper protective infrastructure limit development. Overall, Kutubdia's physical capital remains severely limited and acts as the main constraint within the SLF framework. Despite having strong social interrelations and rich natural assets, tourism cannot be developed in a safe or sustainable manner without significant investment in transport systems, accommodation, public services, healthcare facilities, and coastal protection infrastructure.

Table 2. Overall Livelihood Assets Synthesis based on SLF- for Kutubdia.

Asset Type	Status	Implication for Tourism
Human	Moderate	Needs tourism-specific capacity building
Social	Strong	High community readiness and acceptance
Financial	Moderate–Weak	Risk of elite capture and leakage
Natural	Strong but fragile	High potential, high risk
Physical	Weak	Immediate barrier to development

Table 2 provides a summary of the overall condition of livelihood assets in Kutubdia based on the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) and outlines their implications for tourism development. Human capital is found as moderate, indicating that while basic skills and local experience exist, there is a clear need for tourism-specific training and broader capacity-building initiatives by public and private organizations. Social capital is comparatively strong, reflecting high levels of community cohesion, cooperation, and acceptance of tourism. Financial capital is moderate to weak, suggesting limited capacity for local investment and raising concerns that tourism benefits may be concentrated among a small group or may leak outside the community. Natural capital is found as the strongest asset among the five assets, offering significant tourism potential; however, it remains highly fragile and exposed to environmental risks. In contrast, physical capital is identified as weak and represents the most immediate barrier to tourism development. Poor transport connectivity, insufficient infrastructure, and limited services significantly restrict safe, accessible, and sustainable tourism development, despite the island's other strengths.

5.2. Community Readiness

The findings suggest that the existing livelihood assets in Kutubdia Island play a significant role in shaping community preparedness and willingness to participate in tourism development. Strong social cohesion, positive attitudes towards visitors, and the interest of educated and unemployed young people in tourism-related activities indicate a relatively high level of social readiness within the community. Many

residents viewed tourism as a potential alternative source of livelihood and expressed a willingness to become involved in the sector. Despite this positive attitude, tourism development on the island remains limited due to major weaknesses in physical capital. Poor transport connectivity, inadequate accommodation facilities, weak infrastructure, and limited-service systems continue to restrict tourism growth. As a result, tourism remains largely underdeveloped even though the social conditions for community participation appear favourable. This imbalance highlights that community willingness alone is not enough to support tourism development. Without targeted investment in physical infrastructure and essential services, the tourism potential of Kutubdia is unlikely to be fully realised. This readiness is also reflected in the community's existing capacity to manage large gatherings. As Eskender (Shopkeeper) stated: *"During the festival, thousands of people gather here from all over the country. Shrine committee organizes food and accommodation for all the people for free. We are just like this"*, indicating the community's ability to collectively organize and support visitors. Perceptions of safety and hospitality further reinforce this preparedness. Yasin, a local businessman, explained:

Tourists won't face harassment. It's very safe. In the winter, some young people come here to camp on the Belavumi beach. I can say they never faced any kind of problem from the locals. Sometimes we also sit with them and sing songs for them.

This was echoed by Kaisar, a local fisherman, who highlighted the everyday support offered to visitors, stating,

Our people help them cross the Kutubdia Channel and provide support when needed... If you ask someone, "Brother, can you buy me some fish?" they will buy it for you after you pay them... Tourists who come to Kutubdia generally do not face any major problems. Those who wish to visit can do so without concern, and we are prepared to ensure their safety.

Similarly, Meskat (local restaurant waiter) noted, *"The people of Kutubdia are not bad... Even with so many tourists carrying money, there's no issue. Everything stays safe here. Kutubdia is a much safer place."* These accounts indicate that concerns related to social conflict, crime, or visitor harassment are minimal. Local acceptance of tourism as a source of economic improvement further reflects community readiness. Khalek (fisherman) stated, *"We're happy when people visit. The local people will be happier, and businesses will improve."*

The findings suggest that although the community shows strong readiness and positive attitudes towards tourism, the lack of proper physical capital remains the main barrier to tourism development in Kutubdia Island. Among the limitations, transportation was identified as the most critical challenge, as it directly affects tourist accessibility and mobility. Sadek, a local teacher, clearly highlighted this issue by stating:

The main issue is transportation. If we want to attract tourists, we must create facilities that allow them to visit in the morning and leave by evening. For that, we need a system to facilitate vehicles crossing over, specifically a ferry service. Building a bridge isn't feasible, but if we get a ferry service that allows vehicles and tourists to cross, it would solve many issues.

This finding highlights how the absence of a reliable and safe transport system limits both short-term visits and the overall flow of tourists to the island. Beyond accessibility issues, the findings further reveal a shortage of basic tourism facilities, which negatively affects visitor interest and reduces the length of stay. Hafiz, an auto-rickshaw driver, also pointed to the lack of attractions and supporting services, as he emphasised:

If we had seating chairs on the beach, good restaurants, and nice hotels, more people would come. Right now, people don't come because there's not much to do. There are no good facilities for tourists. Tourists like to eat, but there isn't even a good market where they can buy things... People don't know how beautiful this place is. Many people aren't aware. If we promoted it more, people would definitely come.

This finding also supports previous respondents' consent and also highlights that limited tourism facilities and weak promotion reduce visitor interest and shorten stays. Hafiz, an auto-rickshaw driver, also pointed to the lack of attractions and supporting services, "Also, many people are scared of crossing the river at the ferry point. During the monsoon, the waves are high, and people can't cross. If there were a bridge, many more people could come." This gap in physical capital becomes more evident when residents compare Kutubdia with established destinations. Sabrina, a local resident, directly contrasted the island with Cox's Bazar, stating:

We have a beach here like Cox's Bazar, but people do not visit in the same way. Cox's Bazar has hotels, restaurants, and proper seating areas along the beach. Kutubdia does not have these facilities. We also do not have a regular ferry service. Visitors must cross the sea by small boats or speedboats, which many people find frightening. Those who have never travelled by sea often feel unsafe. If a proper ferry service were available, it would be easier for everyone, including elderly visitors, to travel to the island.

This comparison highlights that the key problem to develop tourism in Kutubdia is not community resistance, but rather the lack of transport infrastructure and visitor facilities. Overall, the findings show that although local willingness and readiness to engage in tourism are strong, insufficient physical capital particularly in transport systems and basic tourism infrastructure prevents this potential from being translated into actual development.

6. Discussion

The SLF theory identifies five capital assets - human, social, natural, physical, and financial - as the core elements supporting community well-being (Kollmair and St. Gamper, 2002). In the context of tourism, the study suggests that Kutubdia Island possesses a mixed range of these assets and capitals (Table 3). Local people strongly value the island’s natural capital, including its pristine sandy beaches, casuarina forests, mangroves, and extensive salt fields, as a ‘treasure trove of natural beauty’ that has long attracted visitors. Yet the findings also indicate that Kutubdia’s infrastructure is ‘underdeveloped’, even as ‘thousands of tourists’ arrive annually (Manik, 2025). This juxtaposition encapsulates the core tension of our findings: This contrast shows a clear gap between potential and reality in Kutubdia’s tourism development.

The community’s human capital shows clear limitations. In Kutubdia, the average literacy rate is nearly 70% (BBS, 2022), which is close to the national average. However, the study reveals gaps in education quality and, more importantly, a lack of tourism-related skills. Although some long-established schools exist, there are no vocational training opportunities in areas such as hospitality or foreign languages. Health services are also limited, as there is only one Upazila health care centre, indicating weak capacity to support labour-intensive tourism activities. As a result, many residents expressed an interest in earning income from tourism but felt unprepared to manage tourism-related activities without proper training. Previous studies have similarly shown that deficiencies in human capital can restrict tourism adaptation and development (Torabi et al. 2024).

Table 3. Community livelihood assets in Kutubdia Island.

Livelihood Assets	Definitions	Consideration for this study
Human assets	Human assets refer to people’s skills, knowledge, capabilities, employment status, health, and personal attributes.	This study considers the education, physical capacity of community members for their respective occupations, and healthcare facilities.
Social assets	It includes social networks, group memberships, and relationships based on trust, as well as associations, affiliations, reciprocity, and exchange.	The relationship among community members, including social support systems, membership in social organisations, and networks of trust, cooperation, and reciprocal exchange.

Financial assets	Financial capital refers to financial resources such as hard cash in hand, income and savings, bank deposits, liquid assets, pensions, and remittances.	Incomes and savings of the local community members.
Natural assets	Natural assets refer to natural resources such as fish stocks, areas of seabed accessed through leases or licences, owned land, cultivated crops, water sources, forest products, natural beauty, and biodiversity	Natural resources of the island (land, water, wildlife, biodiversity, sea beach, and natural beauty).
Physical assets	physical assets refer to basic infrastructure such as roads, water supply, sanitation, energy systems, internal and external transport, and communication networks, as well as hospitality facilities, housing, and the tools and equipment used for production.	Basic infrastructure (roads, jetty, electricity facility etc.), and hospitality infrastructure (hotels and restaurants).

Source: Adopted and modified from McLeod (2001) and Masud et al. (2015).

In contrast, social capital in Kutubdia appears relatively strong, particularly in terms of community networks and social norms. The island's residents maintain close kinship ties and cooperative practices, especially in fishing and salt farming. Community members often share responsibilities and engage in resolving local issues, reflecting a strong sense of collective action. However, the study found no formal tourism associations or cooperatives on the island. Previous research on community-based tourism (CBT) suggests that strong social cohesion can support local empowerment and strengthen community control over tourism activities (Pasanchay and Schott 2021). In Kutubdia, this indicates potential for grassroots tourism development. However, the absence of formal institutions and organised leadership means this potential remains largely unrealised. Without external support, participatory planning, or local leadership, strong social ties alone may not be sufficient to sustain tourism development.

Kutubdia also possesses significant natural resources beyond its scenic beach. Geological reports identify gas and sulphur deposits along with strong wind energy potential (Tanim and Roy 2013). Field observations further confirm resources such as dried fish production, casuarina forests, and salt farming activities. These findings align with previous studies highlighting the untapped tourism potential of Bangladesh's coastal regions (Islam, 2024). However, the island's natural capital remains highly fragile and exposed to environmental risks. Respondents emphasised erosion and climate impacts; over the past fifty years, Kutubdia has lost a large portion of its land, and projections warn it may vanish from the map completely in 70 years if erosion continues (Tanim and Roy 2013). This vulnerability reduces tourism confidence, reflecting the dual role of natural capital as both attraction and risk. As noted in similar contexts, tourism can enhance livelihoods only if supported by adaptive strategies (Hossain et al. 2025).

Financial capital presents a similar contrast. Although activities such as fishing and salt farming provide seasonal income for many households, this income rarely translates into savings, investment, or long-term financial planning that could support tourism-related enterprises. This reflects broader rural conditions where financial capital is essential for livelihood diversification within the SLF framework but often remains weak due to limited access to formal financial systems and weak financial planning practices (Sarnacchiaro & Ariante, 2025). Evidence also shows that many rural adults lack basic skills in budgeting, saving, and long-term financial management, highlighting the need to improve financial literacy (Czech et al. 2024). Despite these constraints, some residents benefit from secure land ownership and relatively independent income sources, which could support local entrepreneurship if appropriate financial support is provided. This may include targeted credit schemes, savings groups, or tourism-related microfinance initiatives. Without such interventions, financial capital is likely to remain limited, increasing the risk of external investor dominance and reducing opportunities for inclusive local development (Hesna et al. 2025).

Among all forms of capital, physical capital emerges as the most significant barrier to tourism development in Kutubdia. Despite its natural attractions, basic infrastructure on the island remains severely underdeveloped. Roads are in poor condition, and there are no regular shipping services or airport facilities. Tourism-related infrastructure is also very limited, with only a few accommodation options apart from a single government guesthouse, no organised tour operators, and unreliable mobile network coverage. During fieldwork, respondents repeatedly noted that the absence of proper accommodation discourages tourist visits.

Studies on community-based tourism (CBT) consistently emphasise the importance of local infrastructure such as transport, healthcare, and communication systems for sustainable tourism development (Pasanchay and Schott 2021). In many rural tourism models, improvements in hospitality services also contribute indirectly to broader community development. However, in Kutubdia, the lack of basic infrastructure means that tourism development cannot begin without substantial external investment. Physical capital remains severely constrained, with weak transport links, inadequate accommodation, limited access to clean water, and insufficient healthcare services all restricting visitor access, comfort, and safety. This aligns with broader evidence that tourism infrastructure is a critical determinant of destination competitiveness, as it enables accessibility and supports the basic requirements of visitors.

Taken together, the livelihood asset profile of Kutubdia Island suggests a cautious but optimistic view of tourism as a potential pathway for sustainable development in a vulnerable coastal context (Tao and Wall 2020). Strong social networks and rich natural attractions help create local interest in tourism. However, limitations in human and financial capital continue to restrict meaningful community participation in tourism-related activities. In this context, physical capital emerges as the key constraint. Without a reliable ferry service, permanent coastal embankments, and basic services such as safe drinking water and healthcare, the island's social and

natural assets cannot be effectively converted into tourism readiness. At the same time, community-based tourism (CBT) requires financial resources, coordination, and long-term planning. For this reason, its development should be supported by government agencies and NGOs through hospitality training and financial literacy programmes (Pasanchay and Schott 2021). Such support is important not only for strengthening local participation but also for reducing the risk of elite control over tourism development. Finally, tourism planning needs to prioritise the protection of Kutubdia's fragile environment, especially ecosystems already under pressure from ongoing environmental degradation.

7. Conclusion

This study assessed community livelihood assets and tourism development readiness in Kutubdia Island, Bangladesh, using the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) as an analytical lens. It examined the condition of human, social, financial, natural, and physical capital and their combined influence on community readiness for tourism development. The findings reveal a clear imbalance across these assets. Social capital is relatively strong, supported by community unity, trust, hospitality, and generally positive attitudes towards visitors, which together create a supportive environment for tourism. Human capital is moderately developed, reflected in educational attainment and youth interest in tourism, but constrained by limited tourism-related skills and limited healthcare services. Natural capital offers strong tourism potential, although it remains highly vulnerable to environmental risks. Financial capital is unevenly distributed, limiting the capacity of many community members to invest in tourism activities. Physical capital is the weakest component and represents the main barrier to tourism development. Despite community interest in tourism, progress is constrained by poor transport infrastructure, a lack of accommodation facilities, and limited basic services.

Methodologically, applying the SLF in a pre-development context shifts its use from evaluating post-development outcomes to assessing baseline conditions before tourism expansion. This approach helps to clarify how different livelihood assets interact and identifies the key structural constraints affecting development. From a policy perspective, tourism planning in Kutubdia should prioritise improvements in physical infrastructure while also strengthening skills development and financial support mechanisms to ensure meaningful local participation and reduce the risk of external capture of benefits. Such measures would also help align tourism development with local strengths and environmental sustainability. The study has some limitations, including its context-specific qualitative design and limited participation of women. Future research could adopt mixed-method approaches, compare different island contexts, and include more diverse participant groups to strengthen evidence-based tourism planning in vulnerable small island settings.

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